

After *Oppenheimer* and The Oscars, A Difficult American Truth: Atomic Bombs Were Not Needed to Win World War II

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*The unleashed power of the atom has changed everything except our ways of thinking,
and thus we drift towards unparalleled catastrophe.¹*

Albert Einstein

The 96th Academy Awards ceremony is ancient television history for most of us now; at best, it is little more than a quickly fading memory from March 2024. Christopher Nolan's blockbuster film, *Oppenheimer*, was the big winner, with seven Oscars, including best picture, director, actor, and supporting actor.

Despite being based on the most highly regarded written history of Oppenheimer and The Manhattan Project,² the film, regrettably, is more a highly fragmented, Hollywood biopic about its title character than it is a helpful history of the first atomic bombs that were dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Japan, eighty years ago this week; why they were used on Japan; and the nuclear arms race they unleashed.³ However, it does, at least, offer us a glimpse into the complicated history of the first atomic bombs and some of the difficult truths behind one of the darkest chapters in our country's history: truths that challenge long-held, American narratives shaped by secrecy, misinformation, propaganda and myth.

Yet despite the immense popularity of this latest film on The Manhattan Project, many Americans still do not know – or choose not to believe - that *atomic bombs were not needed to win World War II*, and that *the U.S. knew well before the bombs were dropped that they were not needed to defeat Nazi Germany or force Japan to surrender*.

Public debates over whether the bombs were needed began within weeks after Japan's surrender,⁴ and continue today. However, many documents have since been declassified, and much historical research has been published. Here is what we know now, eighty years after the first atomic device, nicknamed "The Gadget", was exploded at the "Trinity Test" on July 16, 1945. Three weeks later, on August 6th and 9th, the United States of America dropped the world's first two atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Japan, killing between 110,000 and 210,000 human beings,⁵ most of them, civilians.

There were countless times when the atomic bomb project could have been stopped by those in charge – by our scientists, our military leaders, and our political leaders. Here are three such moments: when decisions were made – or not made⁶ - to continue to build or use the first atomic bombs anyway, despite the knowledge that they were no longer needed to defeat Germany or win the war in the Pacific.

November, 1944. The major initial impetus for scientists' participation in the Manhattan Project was the existential fear that Hitler might gain possession of such a weapon and thus become undefeatable.⁷ However, the U.S. knew for certain that there was no threat of a German atomic bomb at least eight months before the Trinity Test – at least half a year before Germany surrendered in May 1945.

American intelligence had learned by early November that its' secret ALSOS Mission⁸ had been successful; that Germany's nuclear bomb effort had made very little progress. After ALSOS discovered Carl Friedrich von Weizsäcker's papers in Strasburg, Dr. Samuel Goudsmit, the Scientific Chief of ALSOS, submitted a decisive intelligence report to the head of the Manhattan Project, Gen. Leslie Groves, which plainly stated:

*"The conclusions were unmistakable. The evidence ... proved definitely that Germany had no atom bomb and was not likely to have one in any reasonable time. There was no need to fear any [atomic] attack...they were about as far as we were in 1940, before we had begun any large-scale efforts on the atom bomb at all. ...As far as the German scientists were concerned, the whole thing was still on an academic scale."*⁹

In his final report to the chief of military intelligence, the ALSOS Mission's leader subsequently concluded that, "as a result of [Dr. Goudsmit's] report...Gen. Groves...was in a position to inform the War Department and the British Government that the Germans were not ready to employ atomic power in the European Campaign."¹⁰

Simply stated, the leaders of our American government and military (along with the British government) knew by November 1944 that what our scientists feared most - the fundamental purpose behind their participation in the Manhattan Project – had never materialized. The result of this new knowledge? Work on developing America's atomic bombs continued.

April 30-May 8, 1945. Adolf Hitler's death on April 30, 1945, was followed by the unconditional surrender of Nazi Germany to the Allied forces on May 7 (then to the Soviet Union on May 8), and the V-E Day ("Victory in Europe" Day) celebrations on May 8. We might expect, therefore, that our brilliant, intensely logical, Manhattan Project scientists would decide to halt their own work on atomic bombs. The enemy they feared had been defeated, and the U.S. was still months away from even testing "The Gadget".

Some did discuss whether the work should continue, and one in particular, Leo Szilard (the Hungarian-born physicist who initiated and was lead co-author of the famous letter to President Roosevelt signed by Albert Einstein), made multiple, unsuccessful attempts to persuade President Truman, Secretary of State James Byrnes, Oppenheimer, and others not to use the bomb. Not only was the war with Germany over, but Szilard and others feared that the unprecedented use of an atomic bomb would likely start an arms race with the Soviet Union.

In the end, new rationales and justifications replaced those which were no longer valid (for example, that the world should know about the powerful new bomb and its destructive power),

and Oppenheimer's team continued their efforts to build the first atomic bomb. Gen. Leslie Groves and others in the U.S. military urged them to work even faster so the weapon could be used before the war ended.

May-July, 1945. By late spring 1945, American Intelligence had intercepted Japanese cables, stating that Japan was willing to surrender to the U.S. as long as they could “keep their emperor and the constitution, fearing that otherwise a military surrender would only mean the collapse of all order and of all discipline’.”¹¹

*“[T]he President **knew** the Japanese were ‘looking for peace,’ and that the military use of atomic bombs on cities was an option rather than a necessity for ending the war in August.”*¹²

Moreover, the war had devastated Japan even before America’s massive firebombing raids on Tokyo on March 9th and the catastrophic firestorms that followed, which “killed an estimated 100,000 people”¹³. The U.S. then continued firebombing Japan into July until “all but five of Japan’s major cities had been razed and hundreds of thousands of Japanese civilians had been killed.”¹⁴

Per President Roosevelt’s request at the Yalta Conference in February 1945, Stalin agreed that his country would enter the war against Japan three months after Germany surrendered. On April 12th, Henry Truman became president upon Roosevelt’s death. Truman’s own writings while at the Potsdam Conference in July, show that he knew the Soviet Union’s planned entry into the war on August 15th would force Japan to surrender.

Ultimately, however, Truman and his Secretary of State, James F. Byrnes, sought instead to end the war before the Soviet Union entered it, and thereby limit its post-war sphere of influence. They saw the atomic bomb as a way to do exactly that.¹⁵ Byrnes wrote: “...it was ever present in my mind that it was important that we should have an end to the war before the Russians came in.”¹⁶ In the end, however, Stalin declared war on Japan on August 8th (a week early), two days after the destruction of Hiroshima and one day before Nagasaki suffered a similar fate.

President Truman’s ‘decision’¹⁷ to use atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki was, in large part, a geopolitical tactic to limit post-war Soviet power; it was not about needing the bombs to win the war or save American soldiers’ lives. In stark contrast to Truman’s and Byrnes’s Machiavellian speculations about Stalin’s intentions, other leaders focused instead on Japan, the intended target of the bombs: “[Assistant Secretary of War John J.] McCloy and many other ranking officials could see that key members of the Tokyo government were trying to find a way to terminate the war, largely on Washington’s terms.”¹⁸

Chairman of the Joint Chiefs of Staff Adm. William D. Leahy wrote: “The Japanese were already defeated and ready to surrender. The use of this barbarous weapon at Hiroshima and Nagasaki was of no material assistance in our war against Japan. In being the first to use it we...adopted

an ethical standard common to the barbarians of the Dark Ages. I was not taught to make war in that fashion.”¹⁹

When Gen. Dwight D. Eisenhower, the Supreme Allied Commander, “was informed of the existence of the bomb at the Potsdam Conference in July, he told [Secretary of War] Stimson he thought an atomic bombing was unnecessary because ‘the Japanese were ready to surrender and it wasn’t necessary to hit them with that awful thing.’”²⁰ After the war ended, Eisenhower wrote,

“I...voiced my grave misgivings, first on the basis of my belief that Japan was already defeated and that dropping of the bomb was completely unnecessary, and secondly because I thought that our country should avoid shocking world opinion by the use of a weapon whose employment was, I thought, no longer mandatory as a measure to save American lives.”²¹

Even Winston Churchill wrote, “It would be a mistake to suppose that the fate of Japan was settled by the atomic bomb. Her defeat was certain before the first bomb fell.”²²

Coda: The Myth of Saved American Lives. Many Americans believe unfounded post-war justifications that the atomic bombs were dropped on Japan to save the lives of 200,000 – 500,000 American soldiers, who would die in a land invasion of Japan. As the historian, Barton J. Bernstein writes:

“Actually, there is no evidence that any top military planner or major American policy-maker ever believed between May 1945 and Hiroshima that an invasion would cost [a half million] lives. Indeed, there is solid evidence, in declassified files in Washington, that military planners seven weeks before Hiroshima had placed the number at 46,000 and sometimes as low as about 20,000 American lives.

The claim of a half million American lives was a post-war creation.”²³

Contrary to what many Americans still believe, the historical record clearly states that America did not need to kill as many as 210,000 human beings – most of them civilians – in order to end the war; we did not need to create and use new weapons of mass destruction that also kill victims through radioactive poisoning over months and years; nor did we need to open Pandora’s box and thereby begin the nuclear, and then thermonuclear, arms race that to this day threatens all life on earth.

Why did the Manhattan Project scientists continue to build the first atomic bomb after Germany was defeated? Why didn’t they stop?²⁴ Why did our political and military leaders at the highest levels continue the effort to build and drop the first atomic bombs when they were not needed to win World War II? Why did they then mislead the American people and the world by means of mistruths and propaganda campaigns? These are questions every American has a right to ask of our country.

Some will say that there is nothing we can do to change the past. This is an obvious truism. What does matter, however, is that the dark truths behind the history of the atomic bomb have continued to animate the recent past and illuminate the present. The Manhattan Project was a ghostly prologue to what has been the modus operandi of the marriage between, and politics of, science and the arms race – along with the industries that promote, propel and profit from every aspect of it – from 1945 to the present.

Today, nation states - and the social institutions that comprise them (including government, military, business, finance, science, and education) - are in breathlessly accelerating, increasingly competitive races to produce technologies that have profound consequences for the fate of the human race and the fate of our earth, with little, insufficient, or no public knowledge, oversight or permission.

Our burgeoning military-industrial complex in the U.S. could not exist without scientists, engineers, technologists and businesses that engage directly in weapons-related work. To do so, those involved must believe - or have decided - that it is ethical to participate in weapons research, development, procurement, deployment, and/or use. It is also possible, of course, that some people have never even asked themselves this question.

In the specific case of scientists, how do those who engage in weapons-related work, even at theoretical levels, think about the pursuit of knowledge that results – or may possibly result - in weapons of mass destruction; weapons that present an existential threat to all life and the earth itself? Or, do they think that more weapons of mass destruction can actually ‘win’ wars?

If so, they follow much too closely in the footsteps of the Manhattan Project scientists, who thought “that the development of technology would somehow ‘solve’ the social problems of war and peace ... [even though] the roots of the social institution of war...are social (i.e., economic, political, ideological).”²⁵

No individual or group has rights without responsibilities. This is particularly true in a democracy. We all have ethical responsibilities and with them, the power to improve - rather than destroy - the human race and the profoundly exquisite world we inhabit. This applies equally to everyone: our political and military leaders, our teachers, our scientists, engineers and technologists, and our corporations, companies and financiers.

The human efforts to make and drop atomic bombs on other members of our own species in the last century have immense meaning and consequences for the present and future. What lessons, if any, have we learned that will save us from the next Manhattan Project...that will protect us from ourselves?

Back in Hollywood, at the 2024 Academy Awards ceremony, the only acknowledgement of this history, of these American decisions and deeds and the difficult truths behind them, came from Sir Ben Kingsley, when he presented the award for Best Actor: “Cillian Murphy...the performance is masterful, endowing his portrayal with layers of humanity, whilst his character

created something inhuman.” And from Cillian Murphy, when he accepted the award: “...we made a film about the man who created the atomic bomb and, for better or worse, we’re all living in Oppenheimer’s world, so I would really like to dedicate this to the peacemakers everywhere.”

***Noncooperation in military matters should be
an essential moral principle for all true scientists.***

*Albert Einstein*²⁶

¹ Emergency Committee of Atomic Scientists, “First fundraising telegram for the Emergency Committee of Atomic Scientists,” accessed February 5, 2024, <https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/omeka/items/show/20406>. Signed by Albert Einstein. Telegram date: May 23, 1946.

² Kai Bird and Martin J. Sherwin, *American Prometheus: The Triumph and Tragedy of J. Robert Oppenheimer*. NY: Vintage Books. 2005.

³ A much shorter, much better film, *The Day After Trinity: J. Robert Oppenheimer and the Atomic Bomb*, Jon Else’s extraordinary, Peabody Award-winning film, was nominated for an Academy Award for Best Documentary Feature of 1980 and also won a CINE Golden Eagle Award.

⁴ Bird and Sherwin, op. cit., p.318.

⁵ Alex Wellerstein, “Counting the dead at Hiroshima and Nagasaki”. *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*. Aug. 4, 2020. <https://thebulletin.org/2020/08/counting-the-dead-at-hiroshima-and-nagasaki/#post-heading>. Accessed on Jan 28, 2024: “The most credible estimates cluster around a ‘low’ of 110,000 mortalities and a ‘high’ of 210,000, an enormous gap. (The estimates for each city have a range of +/- 10,000.” “Low: 70,000 at Hiroshima + 40,000 at Nagasaki = 110,000.” “High: 140,000 at Hiroshima + 70,000 at Nagasaki = 210,000.”

⁶ In “What journalists should know about the atomic bombings”, Alex Wellerstein points out that Truman’s ‘decision’ was actually a “non-decision”: “As General Groves put it, Truman’s role was ‘one of noninterference – basically, a decision not to upset the existing plans.’” and Truman decided not to upset them. <https://blog.nuclearsecrecy.com/2020/06/09/what-journalists-should-know-about-the-atomic-bombings/>

⁷ Smith, Alice Kimball, *A Peril and A Hope. The Scientists’ Movement in America: 1945-47*, Cambridge: The M.I.T. Press. 1970 (1965). Page 3.

⁸ Goudsmit, Samuel. *Alsos*. Plunkett Lake Press. Kindle Edition. Location 455 of 4148.

Alsos was comprised of both scientific and military team members. Its mission was to follow right behind the Allied Forces as they liberated western Europe from the Nazis, capture their scientists, in order to discover how far along the Germans were in developing an atomic weapon, destroy any progress, steal their uranium, and capture their nuclear scientists.

In his Forward to his book, *Alsos*, Goudsmit writes, “The plain fact of the matter is that the Germans were nowhere near getting the secret of the atom bomb. Indeed, at the rate they were going and the direction they were taking, it is anybody’s guess if they would have arrived at it at all in any practicable period of time. Months after our scientists had established, beyond the shadow of a doubt, the feasibility of the atom bomb, the Germans were still only talking about the “uranium problem” and the possibility of constructing a “uranium machine.” They did not yet know how to produce a chain reaction in a uranium pile. They did not know how to produce plutonium.”

⁹ *Ibid.*, Location 1431 of 4148.

¹⁰ “Final Report, ALSOS Mission to “Chief, Military Intelligence Service” on 10 December, 1945. Unclassified on May 31, 2011. Hoover Institution Library & Archives, Stanford University. <https://digitalcollections.hoover.org/internal/media/dispatcher/267836/full>

¹¹ Allen Dulles “...reported to Assistant Secretary of War John J. McCloy”, in Bird and Sherwin, op. cit., p.300.

¹² *Ibid.*, p.302.

¹³ Ibid., p.291.

¹⁴ Ibid., p.291.

¹⁵ Robert L. Messer, "New Evidence On Truman's Decision", pp. 94-97, in *Hiroshima's Shadow*, Eds. Kai Bird and Lawrence Lifschultz. Stony Creek, CT: The Pamphleteer's Press. 1998.

¹⁶ Bird and Sherwin, op. cit., p.301.

¹⁷ Wellerstein, op.cit., <https://blog.nuclearsecrecy.com/2020/06/09/what-journalists-should-know-about-the-atomic-bombings/>.

¹⁸ Bird and Sherwin, op. cit., p.300.

¹⁹ Joseph Rotblat, "Preface: A Social Conscience For the Nuclear Age", p. xix in Bird and Lawrence Lifschultz. op.cit.

²⁰ Bird and Sherwin, op. cit., p.301.

²¹ Dwight D. Eisenhower, *Mandate for Change*. NY: Doubleday, 1963, pp.312-313. Cited in Joseph Rotblat, Preface: A Social Conscience For the Nuclear Age", p. xix in Bird and Lifschultz, op.cit.

²² Joseph Rotblat, p. xix in Bird and Lawrence Lifschultz. op.cit.

²³ Barton J. Bernstein, "A Post-War Myth: 500,000 U.S. Lives Saved", p. 130, in Bird and Lifschultz, op.cit.

²⁴ Only one scientist left the Manhattan Project after Germany was defeated: Joseph Rotblat, who was awarded the Albert Einstein Peace Prize in 1992, and jointly won the Nobel Peace Prize with the Pugwash Conferences in 1995.

²⁵ Robin J. Crews, *The Crocodile Years: The Traditional Image of Science and Physical Scientists' Participation in Weapons Research*. Doctoral Dissertation. University of Colorado at Boulder. 1985. P.7.

²⁶ This Einstein quote can be found in many texts, e.g., Maris Cakars, *There is no Way To Peace, Peace is the Way*. NY: War Resisters League. 1983.